

Corotational stiffness matrices for 2D frame elements

Rafael L. Rangel¹

¹*Centre Internacional de Mètodes Numèrics a l'Enginyeria (CIMNE), Barcelona, Spain*
rrangel@cimne.upc.edu

January 2023 (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14498308)

Abstract: In this work, the tangent stiffness matrix for the geometrically nonlinear analysis of a two-dimensional frame element subjected to large displacements and rotations, but small deformations, is derived based on the Corotational formulation. The tangent matrix is deduced following two equivalent approaches: variational and energy-based. The resulting tangent stiffness matrix of the element makes up the global stiffness matrix of the structure, which is used in incremental and/or iterative numerical methods to capture the geometric nonlinear response.

Keywords: Structural analysis; Geometric nonlinearity; Corotational; Frame model; Beam element;

1. Introduction

A 2D frame element is a 2-noded plane beam with three degrees-of-freedom per node: two translation components and one rotation. The translations may be referred to global or local coordinate system, while the rotation is always about the out-of-plane axis, being independent of the coordinate system used. The frame element can experience axial and bending effects. For the bending behavior, shear distortion of the cross-sections may be neglected (Euler-Bernoulli theory) or considered in an approximate way (Timoshenko theory). Any cross-section can present normal and shear stresses that lead to three types of internal forces: axial force, shear force, and bending moment.

The Corotational formulation establishes a tangent relation between nodal displacements and forces (i.e. a relation between the variation of these quantities or, equivalently, the derivative of internal forces with respect to displacements) by separating rigid-body motions from strain-producing motions. The rigid-body motions are the element translation and rotation, which do not generate internal forces and are measured with respect to the initial configuration using the global coordinate system. The strain-producing motions are those that deform the element and generate internal forces. These motions are measured with respect to a corotated configuration that translates and rotates with the element so that it eliminates all rigid-body motions. The corotated configuration defines the so-called natural system, which is not exactly a coordinate system, but the set of local displacement and force components that are related to element deformations, called natural displacements and forces.

An important characteristic of the Corotational formulation is that the natural displacements may be considered very small and, therefore, the element can be formulated as linear (infinitesimal strains) in the natural system, with the geometric nonlinearity being introduced in the transformation between the reference systems (natural and global systems). Such characteristic allows the formulation to cope very well with analyses of arbitrarily large rigid motions, but small deformations.

This work is based on the theory presented in [1–8], which has been extensively used in programs developed by the author's research group [9–20].

2. Reference Systems

The displacement and force components of the element may be referred to two systems: the global system of coordinates or the natural system of deformations.

Figure 1 shows a frame element in the plane defined by global axes XY . In the initial configuration, the length of the element is L_0 , the angle with the horizontal axis is β_0 , and the nodal coordinates are (x_1, y_1) for the first node and (x_2, y_2) for the second node. As the structure is loaded, the element moves from its original configuration to a deformed configuration. This movement is defined by node displacements and rotations in the global axes directions, which are grouped in vector $\{d_g\}$ of Eq. (1). These displacements are responsible for three types of element motion: a translation, a rotation, and deformations. The first two are the rigid-body motions that do not produce strains and stresses in the element. The deformations are the motions that effectively produce internal forces and are generated by the natural displacements, relative to the corotated configuration: an elongation u_n , and two relative rotations θ_{n1} and θ_{n2} . The displacement components of the natural system are grouped in vector $\{d_n\}$ of Eq. (2).

Figure 1 – Displacement components in global and natural systems.

$$\{d_g\} = \{d_{x1} \quad d_{y1} \quad \theta_1 \quad d_{x2} \quad d_{y2} \quad \theta_2\}^T \quad (1)$$

$$\{d_n\} = \{u_n \quad \theta_{n1} \quad \theta_{n2}\}^T \quad (2)$$

The element elongation, responsible for axial deformation, is given by the difference of lengths of the deformed and initial configurations, according to Eq. (3), assuming that the length of the deformed configuration (L) is the straight distance between the nodes. The nodal rotations relative to the corotated configuration, responsible for flexural deformations and the arising of bending moments and shear forces, are obtained from the difference of the total rotation of nodes (θ_1 and θ_2) and the rigid-body rotation of the element (α), according to Equations (4) and (5). The rigid-body rotation, in turn, is the difference of angles of the corotated and initial configurations: $\beta - \beta_0$.

$$u_n = L - L_0 \quad (3)$$

$$\theta_{n1} = \theta_1 - \alpha \quad (4)$$

$$\theta_{n2} = \theta_2 - \alpha \quad (5)$$

Figure 2.a shows the positive directions of the resulting nodal forces and moments in the global system, which are grouped in vector $\{f_g\}$ of Eq. (6). Figure 2.b shows the positive directions of the three force components that are generated by the natural displacements: an axial force P , and the two bending moments. These components are grouped in vector $\{f_n\}$ of Eq. (7).

Figure 2 – Force components in (a) global system and (b) natural systems.

$$\{f_g\} = \{f_{x1} \quad f_{y1} \quad M_1 \quad f_{x2} \quad f_{y2} \quad M_2\}^T \quad (6)$$

$$\{f_n\} = \{P \quad M_1 \quad M_2\}^T \quad (7)$$

3. Variational Approach

Using the displacements and forces in both reference systems, the tangent stiffness matrix of the element will be derived. The tangent matrix relates nodal displacements and forces in global system. In fact, due to the nonlinearity, the tangent matrix relates displacement increments to force increments, hence the term “tangent”. In other words, it involves the variation of these quantities. The relation between the variations of global displacements and global forces is obtained from the relation between the variations of other global and natural quantities, as indicated in Fig. 2. The next sections will develop the variational relations of the constitutive law (1), kinematic (2), and equilibrium (3) between the reference systems for obtaining the tangent stiffness matrix in the global system (indicated by $[K_t]$ in Fig. 2).

Figure 3 – Relations between variations of global and natural quantities.

3.1 Displacements and Forces in Natural System (Constitutive Relation)

It was commented that the natural displacements might be considered very small, so engineering (infinitesimal) strains can be used in the natural system (it is also known that engineering strains are problematic in the presence of rigid-body rotation, which is not the case of the natural system). Assuming, also, linear-elastic material behavior and considering the cross-section area to be constant (typical consideration for small strain problems), the axial force is related to the element elongation as follows, where E is the elasticity modulus of the material and A is the element cross-sections area:

$$P = \frac{EA}{L_0} u_n \quad (8)$$

For the flexural behavior, the dimensionless Timoshenko parameter of Eq. (9) and the auxiliary parameters of Eq. (10) are used, where G is the shear modulus of the material and A_s is the effective shear area of the element cross-section. When Euler-Bernoulli theory is used, the Timoshenko parameters is null and the auxiliary parameters are 1.

$$\Omega = \frac{EI}{GA_s L^2} \quad (9)$$

$$\mu = 1 + 12\Omega \quad \lambda = 1 + 3\Omega \quad \gamma = 1 - 6\Omega \quad (10)$$

Based on standard structural analysis results and the use of engineering strains, it is possible to show that the end moments of the element are related to the nodal rotations as follows:

$$M_1 = \frac{4\lambda EI}{\mu L_0} \theta_{n1} + \frac{2\gamma EI}{\mu L_0} \theta_{n2} \quad (11)$$

$$M_2 = \frac{2\gamma EI}{\mu L_0} \theta_{n1} + \frac{4\lambda EI}{\mu L_0} \theta_{n2} \quad (12)$$

Equations (8), (11), and (12) are written in matrix form in Eq. (13) and in compact form in Eq. (14), where $[C_n]$ is the matrix of linear-elastic stiffness coefficients that relates displacements and forces in natural system.

$$\begin{Bmatrix} P \\ M_1 \\ M_2 \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} EA/L_0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 4\lambda EI/\mu L_0 & 2\gamma EI/\mu L_0 \\ 0 & 2\gamma EI/\mu L_0 & 4\lambda EI/\mu L_0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} u_n \\ \theta_{n1} \\ \theta_{n2} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (13)$$

$$\{f_n\} = [C_n] \{d_n\} \quad (14)$$

Since only geometric nonlinearity is considered (physical linearity is preserved), the variations of these quantities are similarly related:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \delta P \\ \delta M_1 \\ \delta M_2 \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} EA/L_0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 4\lambda EI/\mu L_0 & 2\gamma EI/\mu L_0 \\ 0 & 2\gamma EI/\mu L_0 & 4\lambda EI/\mu L_0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \delta u_n \\ \delta \theta_{n1} \\ \delta \theta_{n2} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (15)$$

$$\{\delta f_n\} = [C_n] \{\delta d_n\} \quad (16)$$

3.2 Displacements in Natural and Global Systems (Kinematic Relation)

To find a relation between displacements in natural and global systems, consider a small movement (variation) from the corotated configuration, as shown in Fig. 4. In that figure δd is the vector of net variations (difference of global displacements variations of second and first node), whose components in global system are given in Eq. (17). In the corotated configuration, e_1 is the unit vector in element axial direction and e_2 is the unit vector perpendicular to e_1 (so that the result is a right-handed orthogonal coordinate system). The components in global system of the unit vectors are also given in Eq. (17). The variations of element elongation, δu_n , and rigid-body rotation, $\delta \alpha$, are indicated in the figure.

Figure 4 – Small movement (variation) from the corotated configuration.

$$\{\delta d\} = \begin{Bmatrix} \delta d_{x2} - \delta d_{x1} \\ \delta d_{y2} - \delta d_{y1} \end{Bmatrix} \quad \{e_1\} = \begin{Bmatrix} \cos \beta \\ \sin \beta \end{Bmatrix} \quad \{e_2\} = \begin{Bmatrix} -\sin \beta \\ \cos \beta \end{Bmatrix} \quad (17)$$

For an infinitesimal angle change, the variation of element elongation is obtained by the scalar product between the unit axial vector and the net variations vector, as in Eq. (18), which gives the component of δd projected along the direction of e_1 (in other words, since $\delta L_0 = 0$ then $\delta u_n = \delta L - \delta L_0 = \delta L$). Furthermore, still because of an infinitesimal angle change, the variation of the rigid-body rotation can be approximated by the arc length expressed in Eq. (19).

$$\delta u_n = \{e_1\}^T \{\delta d\} \quad (18)$$

$$L \cdot \delta \alpha = \{e_2\}^T \{\delta d\} \quad (19)$$

By multiplying these vectors and organizing the terms, the variations of element elongation and rigid-body rotation can be related to the variation of nodal displacements in global system as shown in Eq. (20) and Eq. (21), where vectors $\{r\}$ and $\{z\}$ are defined.

$$\delta u_n = \begin{Bmatrix} -\cos \beta & -\sin \beta & 0 & \cos \beta & \sin \beta & 0 \end{Bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \delta d_{x1} \\ \delta d_{y1} \\ \delta \theta_1 \\ \delta d_{x2} \\ \delta d_{y2} \\ \delta \theta_2 \end{Bmatrix} = \{r\}^T \{\delta d_g\} \quad (20)$$

$$\delta \alpha = \frac{1}{L} \begin{Bmatrix} \sin \beta & -\cos \beta & 0 & -\sin \beta & \cos \beta & 0 \end{Bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \delta d_{x1} \\ \delta d_{y1} \\ \delta \theta_1 \\ \delta d_{x2} \\ \delta d_{y2} \\ \delta \theta_2 \end{Bmatrix} = \frac{1}{L} \{z\}^T \{\delta d_g\} \quad (21)$$

We are also interested in the variation of relative nodal rotations. They are obtained from the difference between the variations of total nodal rotations and rigid-body rotation:

$$\delta\theta_{n1} = \delta\theta_1 - \delta\alpha \quad (22)$$

$$\delta\theta_{n2} = \delta\theta_2 - \delta\alpha \quad (23)$$

Expressing the total nodal rotations in terms of the vector of global displacements and using Eq. (21), the previous equations can be rewritten as:

$$\delta\theta_{n1} = \{0 \ 0 \ 1 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0\} \{\delta d_g\} - \frac{1}{L} \{z\}^T \{\delta d_g\} \quad (24)$$

$$\delta\theta_{n2} = \{0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 1\} \{\delta d_g\} - \frac{1}{L} \{z\}^T \{\delta d_g\} \quad (25)$$

These equations are put in matrix form as follows, where matrix $[A]$ is defined to write the expression in a compact form:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \delta\theta_{n1} \\ \delta\theta_{n2} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} - \frac{1}{L} \begin{bmatrix} \{z\}^T \\ \{z\}^T \end{bmatrix} \{\delta d_g\} = [A]^T \{\delta d_g\} \quad (26)$$

Combining Equations (20) and (26) into a single matrix form, we arrive at the relation between the variation of natural and global displacements:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \delta\theta_{n1} \\ \delta\theta_{n2} \\ \delta u_n \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \{r\}^T \\ [A]^T \end{bmatrix} \{\delta d_g\} \quad (27)$$

$$\{\delta d_n\} = [T]^T \{\delta d_g\} \quad (28)$$

The matrix $[T]$, whose transpose relates the variations of natural and global displacements, is identified in Eq. (29). This transformation matrix is the same that relates natural and global forces, and it consists of an expansion and a rotation from the natural system to the global system, as seen in the next section.

$$[T] = \begin{bmatrix} -\cos \beta & -\sin \beta/L & -\sin \beta/L \\ -\sin \beta & \cos \beta/L & \cos \beta/L \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ \cos \beta & \sin \beta/L & \sin \beta/L \\ \sin \beta & -\cos \beta/L & -\cos \beta/L \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (29)$$

3.3 Forces in Natural and Global Systems (Equilibrium Relation)

To relate force components of the natural system to the components of the global system, first a relation between forces in natural and local systems will be established. Figure 5 shows the positive directions of the force components in the natural system, in red, and the nodal forces in the local coordinate system of the element, in green.

Figure 5 – Force components in natural and local systems.

It is clear that the local components of axial force are related to the natural force P as:

$$f'_{x1} = -P \quad f'_{x2} = P \quad (30)$$

Considering a constant shear force along the element and verifying the equilibrium of moments at each node, the local components of transverse force can be expressed in terms of the end moments as:

$$f'_{y1} = \frac{M_1 + M_2}{L} \quad f'_{y2} = -\frac{M_1 + M_2}{L} \quad (31)$$

Using Equations (30) and (31) and noticing that the bending moments are common to natural and local systems, the relation between the force components of both systems is given in Eq. (32), and in compact form in Eq. (33). The matrix $[S]$ is identified as an expansion matrix from natural to local system.

$$\begin{Bmatrix} f'_{x1} \\ f'_{y1} \\ M_1 \\ f'_{x2} \\ f'_{y2} \\ M_2 \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1/L & 1/L \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -1/L & -1/L \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} P \\ M_1 \\ M_2 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (32)$$

$$\{f_l\} = [S]\{f_n\} \quad (33)$$

Now, a relation between nodal forces in local and global systems will be established. Figure 6 shows the nodal forces in local axes system, in green, and in global axes system, in blue.

Figure 6 – Force components in local and global systems.

The equilibrium of forces at each node provides the following relations:

$$f_{x1} = f'_{x1} \cos \beta - f'_{y1} \sin \beta \quad f_{x2} = f'_{x2} \cos \beta - f'_{y2} \sin \beta \quad (34)$$

$$f_{y1} = f'_{x1} \sin \beta + f'_{y1} \cos \beta \quad f_{y2} = f'_{x2} \sin \beta + f'_{y2} \cos \beta \quad (35)$$

Since bending moment components are the same for local and global systems, the relation between local and global nodal forces is given in Eq. (36), and in compact form in Eq. (37). The matrix $[R]$ is identified as a rotation matrix from local to global system.

$$\begin{Bmatrix} f_{x1} \\ f_{y1} \\ M_1 \\ f_{x2} \\ f_{y2} \\ M_2 \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos \beta & -\sin \beta & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \sin \beta & \cos \beta & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \cos \beta & -\sin \beta & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \sin \beta & \cos \beta & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} f'_{x1} \\ f'_{y1} \\ M_1 \\ f'_{x2} \\ f'_{y2} \\ M_2 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (36)$$

$$\{f_g\} = [R]\{f_l\} \quad (37)$$

Using Equations (33) and (37), we can now determine the relation between force components in global and natural systems as follows. Note that the product of the rotation matrix $[R]$ by the expansion matrix $[S]$ results in the same transformation matrix $[T]$, previously given in Eq. (29), that relates the variations of natural and global displacements (see the Principle of Contragradency in Appendix A):

$$\{f_g\} = [R]\{S\}P \quad (38)$$

$$\{f_g\} = [T]\{f_n\} \quad (39)$$

Once the relation between global and natural forces is known, the variation of these quantities, in which we are interested, is then obtained by the product rule:

$$\{\delta f_g\} = [T]\{\delta f_n\} + [\delta T]\{f_n\} \quad (40)$$

In this expression, it is necessary to determine the variation of the transformation matrix $[T]$. The variation of each column of the transformation matrix will be obtained separately. For the first column, $\{T_1\}$, the variation is developed using the chain rule as follows, where vector $\{z\}$ is identified in Eq. (42):

$$\{\delta T_1\} = \delta \{-\cos \beta \quad -\sin \beta \quad 0 \quad \cos \beta \quad \sin \beta \quad 0\}^T \quad (41)$$

$$\{\delta T_1\} = \{\sin \beta \quad -\cos \beta \quad 0 \quad -\sin \beta \quad \cos \beta \quad 0\}^T \delta \beta \quad (42)$$

$$\{\delta T_1\} = \{z\} \delta \beta \quad (43)$$

Observing that $\delta \beta = \delta \alpha$ (since $\delta \beta = \delta \beta_0 + \delta \alpha$ and $\delta \beta_0 = 0$), which is given by Eq. (21), the variation of the first column of the transformation matrix is:

$$\{\delta T_1\} = \frac{1}{L} \{z\} \{z\}^T \{\delta d_g\} \quad (44)$$

The second and third columns, $\{T_2\}$ and $\{T_3\}$, can be written as:

$$\{T_2\} = -\frac{1}{L} \{z\} + \{0 \quad 0 \quad 1 \quad 0 \quad 0 \quad 0\}^T \quad (45)$$

$$\{T_3\} = -\frac{1}{L} \{z\} + \{0 \quad 0 \quad 0 \quad 0 \quad 0 \quad 1\}^T \quad (46)$$

The variation of the constant vectors in these equations are zero, so the variation of the second and third columns are equal. Using the product rule:

$$\{\delta T_2\} = \{\delta T_3\} = \delta \left(-\frac{1}{L} \{z\} \right) = \delta \left(-\frac{1}{L} \right) \{z\} + \left(-\frac{1}{L} \right) \{\delta z\} \quad (47)$$

In the previous expression, it is necessary to find $\delta(-1/L)$ and $\{\delta z\}$. The former is developed using the chain rule:

$$\delta \left(-\frac{1}{L} \right) = -\delta L^{-1} = -(-L^{-2} \delta L) = \frac{\delta L}{L^2} \quad (48)$$

Since $\delta L = \delta L_0 + \delta u_n$ and $\delta L_0 = 0$, and using Eq. (20) to express δu_n , the following result is obtained:

$$\delta \left(-\frac{1}{L} \right) = \frac{\delta u_n}{L^2} = \frac{1}{L^2} \{r\}^T \{\delta d_g\} \quad (49)$$

To find $\{\delta z\}$, the chain rule is applied to get Eq. (51), where vector $\{r\}$ is identified with negative sign. It should be noted again that $\delta\beta = \delta\alpha$, so Eq. (21) is used to express $\delta\alpha$, which leads to the final expression in Eq. (52):

$$\{\delta z\} = \delta \{\sin \beta \quad -\cos \beta \quad 0 \quad -\sin \beta \quad \cos \beta \quad 0\}^T \quad (50)$$

$$\{\delta z\} = \{\cos \beta \quad \sin \beta \quad 0 \quad -\cos \beta \quad -\sin \beta \quad 0\}^T \delta\beta \quad (51)$$

$$\{\delta z\} = -\{r\} \delta\alpha = -\frac{1}{L} \{r\} \{z\}^T \{\delta d_g\} \quad (52)$$

Replacing Equations (49) and (52) into Eq. (47), the following expression is achieved for the variation of the second and third columns of the transformation matrix:

$$\{\delta T_2\} = \{\delta T_3\} = \frac{1}{L^2} \left(\{z\} \{r\}^T + \{r\} \{z\}^T \right) \{\delta d_g\} \quad (53)$$

Now that the variation of the transformation matrix is determined, the relation between the variation of natural and global forces, given in Eq. (40), is completely defined.

3.4 Tangent Stiffness Matrix

All the necessary relations between global and natural quantities have been established in the previous sections in order to develop a variationally consistent tangent stiffness matrix in the global system. These relations are illustrated in Fig. 7, where the bold equation indicates the unknown relation that is being sought. This unknown relation is provided by the tangent matrix, which is also defined as the differentiation of internal global forces with respect to global displacements (tangent to the curve of nodal displacements versus nodal forces).

Figure 7 – Established relations between the variations of global and natural quantities.

Equation (40), at the bottom of Fig. 7, is written as Eq. (54) by separating the columns of $[\delta T]$. Then, Eq. (16), on the right side of Fig. 7, is used to replace the variation of natural forces, and Equations (44) and (53) are used to express the variation of the transformation matrix columns in terms of the variation of global displacements, resulting in Eq. (55). Finally, Eq. (28), at the top of Fig. 7, is used to replace the variation of natural displacements in terms of the variation of global displacements, resulting in Eq. (56):

$$\{\delta f_g\} = [T]\{\delta f_n\} + P\{\delta T_1\} + M_1\{\delta T_2\} + M_2\{\delta T_3\} \quad (54)$$

$$\{\delta f_g\} = [T][C_n]\{\delta d_n\} + \frac{P}{L}\{z\}\{z\}^T\{\delta d_g\} + \frac{M_1 + M_2}{L^2}\left(\{z\}\{r\}^T + \{r\}\{z\}^T\right)\{\delta d_g\} \quad (55)$$

$$\{\delta f_g\} = [T][C_n][T]^T\{\delta d_g\} + \frac{P}{L}\{z\}\{z\}^T\{\delta d_g\} + \frac{M_1 + M_2}{L^2}\left(\{z\}\{r\}^T + \{r\}\{z\}^T\right)\{\delta d_g\} \quad (56)$$

Observing that $\{\delta d_g\}$ is a common factor on the right hand side, the relation between variations of global forces and global displacements is finally reached:

$$\{\delta f_g\} = \left[[T][C_n][T]^T + \frac{P}{L}\{z\}\{z\}^T + \frac{M_1 + M_2}{L^2}\left(\{z\}\{r\}^T + \{r\}\{z\}^T\right) \right] \{\delta d_g\} \quad (57)$$

Where the tangent stiffness matrix is identified as:

$$[K_t] = [T][C_n][T]^T + \frac{P}{L}\{z\}\{z\}^T + \frac{M_1 + M_2}{L^2}\left(\{z\}\{r\}^T + \{r\}\{z\}^T\right) \quad (58)$$

This expression provides the tangent stiffness matrix of a 2D frame element in the global coordinate system. The result of multiplying all terms of this expression is given bellow, where c and s stand for $\cos(\beta)$ and $\sin(\beta)$, respectively (remember, for Euler-Bernoulli theory $\mu = \lambda = \gamma = 1$):

$$[K_t] = \begin{bmatrix} k_1 & -k_3 & -k_5 & -k_1 & k_3 & -k_5 \\ & k_2 & k_4 & k_3 & -k_2 & k_4 \\ & & k_7 & k_5 & -k_4 & k_6 \\ & & & k_1 & -k_3 & k_5 \\ \text{sym} & & & & k_2 & -k_4 \\ & & & & & k_7 \end{bmatrix} \quad (59)$$

$$k_1 = (EAL^2c^2\mu + PLL_0s^2\mu - 2(M_1 + M_2)L_0cs\mu + 4EIs^2(2\lambda + \gamma)) / (L^2L_0\mu)$$

$$k_2 = (EAL^2s^2\mu + PLL_0c^2\mu + 2(M_1 + M_2)L_0cs\mu + 4EIs^2(2\lambda + \gamma)) / (L^2L_0\mu)$$

$$k_3 = ((4EI(2\lambda + \gamma) - EAL^2\mu + PLL_0\mu)cs - (M_1 + M_2)(c^2 - s^2)L_0\mu) / (L^2L_0\mu)$$

$$k_4 = (2EIc(2\lambda + \gamma)) / (LL_0\mu)$$

$$k_5 = (2EIs(2\lambda + \gamma)) / (LL_0\mu)$$

$$k_6 = (2EI\gamma) / (L_0\mu)$$

$$k_7 = (4EI\lambda) / (L_0\mu)$$

It should be noted that the tangent matrix is originated by the sum of two stiffness components. In Eq. (58), the first term, which depends on the matrix of linear-elastic stiffness coefficients $[C_n]$, corresponds to the elastic stiffness matrix $[K_e]$. The remaining terms, which depend on element internal forces, originate the geometric stiffness matrix $[K_g]$:

$$[K_e] = [T][C_n][T]^T \quad (60)$$

$$[K_g] = \frac{P}{L} \{z\} \{z\}^T + \frac{M_1 + M_2}{L^2} (\{z\} \{r\}^T + \{r\} \{z\}^T) \quad (61)$$

Another way of looking at the expression of the geometric stiffness matrix is to replace the bending moments by the local shear force, as in Eq. (31). Using here Q as f'_{y1} :

$$[K_g] = \frac{P}{L} \{z\} \{z\}^T + \frac{Q}{L} (\{z\} \{r\}^T + \{r\} \{z\}^T) \quad (62)$$

Considering an element with its local axes aligned with the global axes (i.e. assuming $\beta = 0$), we can check the results for the elastic and geometric stiffness matrices referred to the local coordinate system of the element. Following is the elastic matrix in the local axes system, with general stiffness coefficients that work for Timoshenko or Euler-Bernoulli theory:

$$[K_e] = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{EA}{L_0} & 0 & 0 & -\frac{EA}{L_0} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{4EI(2\lambda + \gamma)}{L^2 L_0 \mu} & \frac{2EI(2\lambda + \gamma)}{LL_0 \mu} & 0 & -\frac{4EI(2\lambda + \gamma)}{L^2 L_0 \mu} & \frac{2EI(2\lambda + \gamma)}{LL_0 \mu} \\ 0 & \frac{2EI(2\lambda + \gamma)}{LL_0 \mu} & \frac{4EI\lambda}{L_0 \mu} & 0 & -\frac{2EI(2\lambda + \gamma)}{LL_0 \mu} & \frac{2EI\gamma}{L_0 \mu} \\ -\frac{EA}{L_0} & 0 & 0 & \frac{EA}{L_0} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -\frac{4EI(2\lambda + \gamma)}{L^2 L_0 \mu} & -\frac{2EI(2\lambda + \gamma)}{LL_0 \mu} & 0 & \frac{4EI(2\lambda + \gamma)}{L^2 L_0 \mu} & -\frac{2EI(2\lambda + \gamma)}{LL_0 \mu} \\ 0 & \frac{2EI(2\lambda + \gamma)}{LL_0 \mu} & \frac{2EI\gamma}{L_0 \mu} & 0 & -\frac{2EI(2\lambda + \gamma)}{LL_0 \mu} & \frac{4EI\lambda}{L_0 \mu} \end{bmatrix} \quad (63)$$

The geometric stiffness matrix in local system is presented next, where local shear force Q is replacing $(M_1 + M_2)/L$:

$$[K_g] = \frac{1}{L} \begin{bmatrix} 0 & Q & 0 & 0 & -Q & 0 \\ Q & P & 0 & -Q & -P & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -Q & 0 & 0 & Q & 0 \\ -Q & -P & 0 & Q & P & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (64)$$

Remember that the assumption for formulating the element in the natural system was that deformations are very small, so engineering strain was used to relate axial force and element elongation. As a result, the geometric stiffness matrix does not contribute with axial rigidity by increasing or decreasing the element stiffness in a pure axial motion. The main effect of the geometric stiffness is on the rotational rigid-body motion of the element.

One way to consider the effect of a large element elongation is to use nonlinear strain measurements, the other is to assume a constant length when deriving the geometric matrix (see related work by the author on the consideration of large deformations of a truss element). The second option would lead to the following geometric matrix, which is invariant with respect to rotations (it is identical in the local and global coordinate systems):

$$[K_g] = \frac{1}{L} \begin{bmatrix} P & Q & 0 & -P & -Q & 0 \\ Q & P & 0 & -Q & -P & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -P & -Q & 0 & P & Q & 0 \\ -Q & -P & 0 & Q & P & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (65)$$

It is also interesting to observe that it would not be possible to derive the geometric stiffness matrix directly in the local system. Trying to do so would result in a nonsymmetrical matrix, with only the terms in positions (2,1), (2,4), (5,1), and (5,4). The terms with axial force P would vanish because they originate from the variation of the first column of transformation matrix $[T]$ (the same as vector $\{r\}$), which would be a constant vector if the local X-axis of the element coincides with global X-axis. The shear force terms that originate from the second product inside the parenthesis of Eq. (62) would also vanish because this term comes from the product rule application in Eq. (47) as result of vector $\{z\}$ being a function of the rotation angle (it would be a constant vector if dealing with local system). The reason for this is that the local and natural systems are aligned, so a transformation between these systems would not cause the internal forces to change direction, which is the effect captured by the geometric stiffness.

4. Energy-Based Approach

The tangent stiffness matrix of the 2D frame element could be derived by directly applying constitutive, kinematic and equilibrium relations between the two reference systems because of the relative simplicity of this element. A more general approach for dealing with complex finite elements is based on energy principles. For the frame element studied here, the potential energy is:

$$U = \frac{1}{2} P u_n + \frac{1}{2} M_1 \theta_{n1} + \frac{1}{2} M_2 \theta_{n2} \quad (66)$$

As explained in section 3.1, stiffness coefficients based on the use engineering strain are used in the natural system of the Corotational formulation. Therefore, according to Equations (8), (11) and (12), the previous expression is rewritten as follows (Timoshenko parameters will be omitted for sake of simplicity):

$$U = \frac{1}{2} \frac{EA}{L_0} u_n^2 + \frac{EI}{L_0} (2\theta_{n1} + \theta_{n2}) \theta_{n1} + \frac{EI}{L_0} (\theta_{n1} + 2\theta_{n2}) \theta_{n2} \quad (67)$$

Multiplying and organizing the terms leads to the following expression for potential energy:

$$U = \frac{1}{2} \frac{EA}{L_0} u_n^2 + \frac{2EI}{L_0} \theta_{n1}^2 + \frac{2EI}{L_0} \theta_{n2}^2 + \frac{2EI}{L_0} \theta_{n1} \theta_{n2} \quad (68)$$

4.1 Internal Forces Vector

The first derivative of the potential energy with respect to the vector of global nodal displacements gives us the internal force vector in the global system:

$$\{f_g\} = \frac{\partial U}{\partial \{d_g\}} \quad (69)$$

Applying the chain and product rules to derive the potential energy, we obtain:

$$\{f_g\} = \frac{EA}{L_0} u_n \frac{\partial u_n}{\partial \{d_g\}} + \frac{4EI}{L_0} \theta_{n1} \frac{\partial \theta_{n1}}{\partial \{d_g\}} + \frac{4EI}{L_0} \theta_{n2} \frac{\partial \theta_{n2}}{\partial \{d_g\}} + \frac{2EI}{L_0} \left(\theta_{n1} \frac{\partial \theta_{n2}}{\partial \{d_g\}} + \theta_{n2} \frac{\partial \theta_{n1}}{\partial \{d_g\}} \right) \quad (70)$$

To evaluate this expression, it is necessary to calculate the first derivatives of natural displacements with respect to the vector of global displacements.

First, we start with the derivatives of element elongation with respect to global displacements. To do so, we express the elongation as the difference of deformed and initial lengths and note that the derivatives of the initial length with respect to global displacements are null, leaving only the deformed length, which is written in terms of initial coordinates and global displacements in Eq. (72).

$$\frac{\partial u_n}{\partial \{d_g\}} = \frac{\partial(L-L_0)}{\partial \{d_g\}} = \frac{\partial L}{\partial \{d_g\}} \quad (71)$$

$$L = \sqrt{\left((x_2 + dx_2) - (x_1 + dx_1)\right)^2 + \left((y_2 + dy_2) - (y_1 + dy_1)\right)^2} \quad (72)$$

By performing the calculations, we arrive at the following result for the first derivative of element elongation with respect to the vector of global displacements (note that it corresponds to Eq. (20)):

$$\frac{\partial u_n}{\partial \{d_g\}} = \left\{ \frac{\partial L}{\partial d_{x1}} \quad \frac{\partial L}{\partial d_{y1}} \quad \frac{\partial L}{\partial \theta_1} \quad \frac{\partial L}{\partial d_{x2}} \quad \frac{\partial L}{\partial d_{y2}} \quad \frac{\partial L}{\partial \theta_2} \right\}^T = \begin{Bmatrix} -\cos \beta \\ -\sin \beta \\ 0 \\ \cos \beta \\ \sin \beta \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (73)$$

Now, we determine the first derivatives of relative rotations with respect to global displacements. To do so, we express the relative rotations as the difference of total nodal rotations and rigid-body rotation:

$$\frac{\partial \theta_{n1}}{\partial \{d_g\}} = \frac{\partial(\theta_1 - \alpha)}{\partial \{d_g\}} = \frac{\partial \theta_1}{\partial \{d_g\}} - \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial \{d_g\}} \quad (74)$$

$$\frac{\partial \theta_{n2}}{\partial \{d_g\}} = \frac{\partial(\theta_2 - \alpha)}{\partial \{d_g\}} = \frac{\partial \theta_2}{\partial \{d_g\}} - \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial \{d_g\}} \quad (75)$$

The derivatives of total nodal rotations with respect to the vector of global displacements are straightforward to obtain:

$$\frac{\partial \theta_1}{\partial \{d_g\}} = \{0 \quad 0 \quad 1 \quad 0 \quad 0 \quad 0\}^T \quad (76)$$

$$\frac{\partial \theta_2}{\partial \{d_g\}} = \{0 \quad 0 \quad 0 \quad 0 \quad 0 \quad 1\}^T \quad (77)$$

To calculate the derivatives of rigid-body rotation with respect to global displacements, we express the rigid-body rotation as the difference of angles between the corotated and initial configurations, in Eq. (78). Since the derivatives of the initial angle with respect to global displacements are null, only the corotated angle remains, which is written in terms of initial coordinates and global displacements in Eq. (79).

$$\frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial \{d_g\}} = \frac{\partial (\beta - \beta_0)}{\partial \{d_g\}} = \frac{\partial \beta}{\partial \{d_g\}} \quad (78)$$

$$\beta = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{(y_2 + d_{y2}) - (y_1 + d_{y1})}{(x_2 + d_{x2}) - (x_1 + d_{x1})} \right) \quad (79)$$

By performing the calculations, we arrive at the following result for the first derivative of rigid-body rotation with respect to the vector of global displacements (note that it corresponds to Eq. (21)):

$$\frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial \{d_g\}} = \left\{ \frac{\partial \beta}{\partial d_{x1}} \quad \frac{\partial \beta}{\partial d_{y1}} \quad \frac{\partial \beta}{\partial \theta_1} \quad \frac{\partial \beta}{\partial d_{x2}} \quad \frac{\partial \beta}{\partial d_{y2}} \quad \frac{\partial \beta}{\partial \theta_2} \right\}^T = \begin{Bmatrix} \sin \beta/L \\ -\cos \beta/L \\ 0 \\ -\sin \beta/L \\ \cos \beta/L \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (80)$$

With the results reached in Equations (76), (77), and (80), we can obtain the first derivatives of relative rotations with respect to global displacements, that we were trying to calculate in Equations (74) and (75) (note that these results correspond to Equations (24) and (25)):

$$\frac{\partial \theta_{n1}}{\partial \{d_g\}} = \begin{Bmatrix} -\sin \beta/L \\ \cos \beta/L \\ 1 \\ \sin \beta/L \\ -\cos \beta/L \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} \quad \frac{\partial \theta_{n2}}{\partial \{d_g\}} = \begin{Bmatrix} -\sin \beta/L \\ \cos \beta/L \\ 0 \\ \sin \beta/L \\ -\cos \beta/L \\ 1 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (81)$$

Now that we have all the first derivatives of natural displacements with respect to global displacements, the vector of global internal forces of Eq. (70) is known. By replacing the derivative results and arranging the terms:

$$\{f_g\} = \frac{EA}{L_0} u_n \begin{Bmatrix} -\cos \beta \\ -\sin \beta \\ 0 \\ \cos \beta \\ \sin \beta \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} + \frac{2EI}{L_0} (2\theta_{n1} + \theta_{n2}) \begin{Bmatrix} -\sin \beta/L \\ \cos \beta/L \\ 1 \\ \sin \beta/L \\ -\cos \beta/L \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} + \frac{2EI}{L_0} (2\theta_{n2} + \theta_{n1}) \begin{Bmatrix} -\sin \beta/L \\ \cos \beta/L \\ 0 \\ \sin \beta/L \\ -\cos \beta/L \\ 1 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (82)$$

By recognizing the natural force components in the previous equation, the vector of global internal forces is rewritten in Eq. (83) and put in matrix form in Eq. (84), which is the same result previously obtained in Eq. (39).

$$\{f_g\} = P \begin{Bmatrix} -\cos \beta \\ -\sin \beta \\ 0 \\ \cos \beta \\ \sin \beta \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} + M_1 \begin{Bmatrix} -\sin \beta/L \\ \cos \beta/L \\ 1 \\ \sin \beta/L \\ -\cos \beta/L \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} + M_2 \begin{Bmatrix} -\sin \beta/L \\ \cos \beta/L \\ 0 \\ \sin \beta/L \\ -\cos \beta/L \\ 1 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (83)$$

$$\{f_g\} = \begin{bmatrix} -\cos \beta & -\sin \beta/L & -\sin \beta/L \\ -\sin \beta & \cos \beta/L & \cos \beta/L \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ \cos \beta & \sin \beta/L & \sin \beta/L \\ \sin \beta & -\cos \beta/L & -\cos \beta/L \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} P \\ M_1 \\ M_2 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (84)$$

4.2 Tangent Stiffness Matrix

The tangent stiffness is found by taking the second derivative of the potential energy with respect to the global displacements vector:

$$[K_t] = \frac{\partial^2 U}{\partial \{d_g\}^2} \quad (85)$$

This is the same of taking the first derivative of the vector of internal forces with respect to the global displacements vector.

$$[K_t] = \frac{\partial^2 U}{\partial \{d_g\}^2} = \frac{\partial \{f_g\}}{\partial \{d_g\}} \quad (86)$$

Writing the vector of internal forces as in Eq. (70), we get:

$$[K_t] = \frac{\partial}{\partial \{d_g\}} \left(\frac{EA}{L_0} u_n \frac{\partial u_n}{\partial \{d_g\}} + \frac{4EI}{L_0} \theta_{n1} \frac{\partial \theta_{n1}}{\partial \{d_g\}} + \frac{4EI}{L_0} \theta_{n2} \frac{\partial \theta_{n2}}{\partial \{d_g\}} + \frac{2EI}{L_0} \theta_{n1} \frac{\partial \theta_{n2}}{\partial \{d_g\}} + \frac{2EI}{L_0} \theta_{n2} \frac{\partial \theta_{n1}}{\partial \{d_g\}} \right) \quad (87)$$

The product rule is used to derive each term inside the parenthesis. The result is the expression of the tangent stiffness matrix of the frame element in Eq. (88). In that equation, the terms that depend on the first derivatives of natural displacements with respect to the vector of global displacements (first ‘‘column’’) account for the elastic stiffness. The terms that depend on the second derivatives of natural displacements with respect to the vector of global displacements (second ‘‘column’’) account for the geometric stiffness.

$$\begin{aligned}
[K_t] = & \frac{EA}{L_0} \left\{ \frac{\partial u_n}{\partial \{d_g\}} \right\} \left\{ \frac{\partial u_n}{\partial \{d_g\}} \right\}^T + \frac{EA}{L_0} u_n \left[\frac{\partial^2 u_n}{\partial \{d_g\}^2} \right] + \\
& \frac{4EI}{L_0} \left\{ \frac{\partial \theta_{n1}}{\partial \{d_g\}} \right\} \left\{ \frac{\partial \theta_{n1}}{\partial \{d_g\}} \right\}^T + \frac{4EI}{L_0} \theta_{n1} \left[\frac{\partial^2 \theta_{n1}}{\partial \{d_g\}^2} \right] + \\
& \frac{4EI}{L_0} \left\{ \frac{\partial \theta_{n2}}{\partial \{d_g\}} \right\} \left\{ \frac{\partial \theta_{n2}}{\partial \{d_g\}} \right\}^T + \frac{4EI}{L_0} \theta_{n2} \left[\frac{\partial^2 \theta_{n2}}{\partial \{d_g\}^2} \right] + \\
& \frac{2EI}{L_0} \left\{ \frac{\partial \theta_{n2}}{\partial \{d_g\}} \right\} \left\{ \frac{\partial \theta_{n1}}{\partial \{d_g\}} \right\}^T + \frac{2EI}{L_0} \theta_{n1} \left[\frac{\partial^2 \theta_{n2}}{\partial \{d_g\}^2} \right] + \\
& \frac{2EI}{L_0} \left\{ \frac{\partial \theta_{n1}}{\partial \{d_g\}} \right\} \left\{ \frac{\partial \theta_{n2}}{\partial \{d_g\}} \right\}^T + \frac{2EI}{L_0} \theta_{n2} \left[\frac{\partial^2 \theta_{n1}}{\partial \{d_g\}^2} \right]
\end{aligned} \tag{88}$$

The elastic stiffness matrix could be evaluated with no further derivations, since we already have the first derivatives of natural displacements with respect to global displacements. However, to evaluate the geometric stiffness matrix, it is necessary to determine the second derivatives of natural displacements with respect to global displacements (this is equivalent to obtaining the variation of transformation matrix $[T]$ in Eq. (40)).

First, we start with the second derivatives of element elongation. Recall, from Eq. (71), that taking the derivative of the element elongation with respect to the global displacements vector is the same as taking the derivative of the deformed length. Therefore, for the second derivative:

$$\frac{\partial^2 L}{\partial \{d_g\}^2} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial^2 L}{\partial d_{x1}^2} & \frac{\partial^2 L}{\partial d_{x1} \partial d_{y1}} & \frac{\partial^2 L}{\partial d_{x1} \partial \theta_1} & \frac{\partial^2 L}{\partial d_{x1} \partial d_{x2}} & \frac{\partial^2 L}{\partial d_{x1} \partial d_{y2}} & \frac{\partial^2 L}{\partial d_{x1} \partial \theta_2} \\ & \frac{\partial^2 L}{\partial d_{y1}^2} & \frac{\partial^2 L}{\partial d_{y1} \partial \theta_1} & \frac{\partial^2 L}{\partial d_{y1} \partial d_{x2}} & \frac{\partial^2 L}{\partial d_{y1} \partial d_{y2}} & \frac{\partial^2 L}{\partial d_{y1} \partial \theta_2} \\ & & \frac{\partial^2 L}{\partial \theta_1^2} & \frac{\partial^2 L}{\partial \theta_1 \partial d_{x2}} & \frac{\partial^2 L}{\partial \theta_1 \partial d_{y2}} & \frac{\partial^2 L}{\partial \theta_1 \partial \theta_2} \\ & & & \frac{\partial^2 L}{\partial d_{x2}^2} & \frac{\partial^2 L}{\partial d_{x2} \partial d_{y2}} & \frac{\partial^2 L}{\partial d_{x2} \partial \theta_2} \\ & \text{sym} & & & \frac{\partial^2 L}{\partial d_{y2}^2} & \frac{\partial^2 L}{\partial d_{y2} \partial \theta_2} \\ & & & & & \frac{\partial^2 L}{\partial \theta_2^2} \end{bmatrix} \tag{89}$$

Then, based on the expression of the deformed length of Eq. (72), the results of the second derivatives of the element elongation with respect to each component of the vector of global displacements are:

$$\frac{\partial^2 u_n}{\partial \{d_g\}^2} = \frac{\partial^2 L}{\partial \{d_g\}^2} = \frac{1}{L} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (90)$$

To determine the second derivatives of relative rotations with respect to the vector of global displacements, recall from Equations (74) and (75) that the derivative of a relative rotation is given by the difference of derivatives of total nodal rotation and rigid body rotation. Therefore, for the second derivatives:

$$\frac{\partial \theta_{n1}}{\partial \{d_g\}} = \frac{\partial^2 \theta_1}{\partial \{d_g\}^2} - \frac{\partial^2 \alpha}{\partial \{d_g\}^2} \quad (91)$$

$$\frac{\partial \theta_{n2}}{\partial \{d_g\}} = \frac{\partial^2 \theta_2}{\partial \{d_g\}^2} - \frac{\partial^2 \alpha}{\partial \{d_g\}^2} \quad (92)$$

Since the second derivatives of total nodal rotations with respect to global displacements are null, the second derivatives of both relative rotations are equal and they will be referred to as θ_n . Recall, also, from Eq. (78), that taking the derivative of rigid-body rotation with respect to the global displacements vector is the same as taking the derivative of the angle of corotated configuration. Therefore, we arrive at:

$$\frac{\partial^2 \theta_n}{\partial \{d_g\}^2} = -\frac{\partial^2 \alpha}{\partial \{d_g\}^2} = -\frac{\partial^2 \beta}{\partial \{d_g\}^2} \quad (93)$$

in which:

$$\frac{\partial^2 \beta}{\partial \{d_g\}^2} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial^2 \beta}{\partial d_{x1}^2} & \frac{\partial^2 \beta}{\partial d_{x1} \partial d_{y1}} & \frac{\partial^2 \beta}{\partial d_{x1} \partial \theta_1} & \frac{\partial^2 \beta}{\partial d_{x1} \partial d_{x2}} & \frac{\partial^2 \beta}{\partial d_{x1} \partial d_{y2}} & \frac{\partial^2 \beta}{\partial d_{x1} \partial \theta_2} \\ & \frac{\partial^2 \beta}{\partial d_{y1}^2} & \frac{\partial^2 \beta}{\partial d_{y1} \partial \theta_1} & \frac{\partial^2 \beta}{\partial d_{y1} \partial d_{x2}} & \frac{\partial^2 \beta}{\partial d_{y1} \partial d_{y2}} & \frac{\partial^2 \beta}{\partial d_{y1} \partial \theta_2} \\ & & \frac{\partial^2 \beta}{\partial \theta_1^2} & \frac{\partial^2 \beta}{\partial \theta_1 \partial d_{x2}} & \frac{\partial^2 \beta}{\partial \theta_1 \partial d_{y2}} & \frac{\partial^2 \beta}{\partial \theta_1 \partial \theta_2} \\ & & & \frac{\partial^2 \beta}{\partial d_{x2}^2} & \frac{\partial^2 \beta}{\partial d_{x2} \partial d_{y2}} & \frac{\partial^2 \beta}{\partial d_{x2} \partial \theta_2} \\ & \text{sym} & & & \frac{\partial^2 \beta}{\partial d_{y2}^2} & \frac{\partial^2 \beta}{\partial d_{y2} \partial \theta_2} \\ & & & & & \frac{\partial^2 \beta}{\partial \theta_2^2} \end{bmatrix} \quad (94)$$

Based on the expression of the corotated angle of Eq. (79), the results of the second derivatives of relative rotations with respect to each component of the vector of global displacements are shown below, where c and s stand for $\cos(\beta)$ and $\sin(\beta)$, respectively.

$$\frac{\partial^2 \theta_n}{\partial \{d_g\}^2} = -\frac{\partial^2 \beta}{\partial \{d_g\}^2} = \frac{1}{L^2} \begin{bmatrix} -2cs & c^2 - s^2 & 0 & 2cs & s^2 - c^2 & 0 \\ c^2 - s^2 & 2cs & 0 & s^2 - c^2 & -2cs & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 2cs & s^2 - c^2 & 0 & -2cs & c^2 - s^2 & 0 \\ s^2 - c^2 & -2cs & 0 & c^2 - s^2 & 2cs & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (95)$$

Now that we have all the second derivatives of natural displacements with respect to global displacements, we can move to the evaluation of the stiffness matrices.

Starting with the elastic stiffness matrix, whose expression is given in Eq. (96), we can evaluate it using the results obtained for the first derivatives of natural displacements with respect to global displacements. The resulting matrix is referred to the global coordinate system and will not be shown due to space saving, but the elastic matrix referred to the local system (i.e. assuming $\beta = 0$) is given in Eq. (97) considering Euler-Bernoulli theory, which is the same matrix of Eq. (63).

$$[K_e] = \frac{EA}{L_0} \left\{ \frac{\partial u_n}{\partial \{d_g\}} \right\} \left\{ \frac{\partial u_n}{\partial \{d_g\}} \right\}^T + \frac{4EI}{L_0} \left\{ \frac{\partial \theta_{n1}}{\partial \{d_g\}} \right\} \left\{ \frac{\partial \theta_{n1}}{\partial \{d_g\}} \right\}^T + \frac{4EI}{L_0} \left\{ \frac{\partial \theta_{n2}}{\partial \{d_g\}} \right\} \left\{ \frac{\partial \theta_{n2}}{\partial \{d_g\}} \right\}^T + \frac{2EI}{L_0} \left\{ \frac{\partial \theta_{n2}}{\partial \{d_g\}} \right\} \left\{ \frac{\partial \theta_{n1}}{\partial \{d_g\}} \right\}^T + \frac{2EI}{L_0} \left\{ \frac{\partial \theta_{n1}}{\partial \{d_g\}} \right\} \left\{ \frac{\partial \theta_{n2}}{\partial \{d_g\}} \right\}^T \quad (96)$$

$$[K_e] = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{EA}{L_0} & 0 & 0 & -\frac{EA}{L_0} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{12EI}{L^2 L_0} & \frac{6EI}{LL_0} & 0 & -\frac{12EI}{L^2 L_0} & \frac{6EI}{LL_0} \\ 0 & \frac{6EI}{LL_0} & \frac{4EI}{L_0} & 0 & -\frac{6EI}{LL_0} & \frac{2EI}{L_0} \\ -\frac{EA}{L_0} & 0 & 0 & \frac{EA}{L_0} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -\frac{12EI}{L^2 L_0} & -\frac{6EI}{LL_0} & 0 & \frac{12EI}{L^2 L_0} & -\frac{6EI}{LL_0} \\ 0 & \frac{6EI}{LL_0} & \frac{2EI}{L_0} & 0 & -\frac{6EI}{LL_0} & \frac{4EI}{L_0} \end{bmatrix} \quad (97)$$

The expression of the geometric stiffness matrix is given in Eq. (98). By arranging the terms, we get Eq. (99), in which it is possible to identify the presence of the bending moments inside the parenthesis, besides the axial force in the first term, resulting in Eq. (100).

$$\begin{aligned}
[K_g] = & \frac{EA}{L_0} u_n \left[\frac{\partial^2 u_n}{\partial \{d_g\}^2} \right] + \\
& \frac{4EI}{L_0} \theta_{n1} \left[\frac{\partial^2 \theta_n}{\partial \{d_g\}^2} \right] + \frac{4EI}{L_0} \theta_{n2} \left[\frac{\partial^2 \theta_n}{\partial \{d_g\}^2} \right] + \frac{2EI}{L_0} \theta_{n1} \left[\frac{\partial^2 \theta_n}{\partial \{d_g\}^2} \right] + \frac{2EI}{L_0} \theta_{n2} \left[\frac{\partial^2 \theta_n}{\partial \{d_g\}^2} \right]
\end{aligned} \tag{98}$$

$$[K_g] = \frac{EA}{L_0} u_n \left[\frac{\partial^2 u_n}{\partial \{d_g\}^2} \right] + \left(\frac{4EI}{L_0} \theta_{n1} + \frac{2EI}{L_0} \theta_{n2} + \frac{2EI}{L_0} \theta_{n1} + \frac{4EI}{L_0} \theta_{n2} \right) \left[\frac{\partial^2 \theta_n}{\partial \{d_g\}^2} \right] \tag{99}$$

$$[K_g] = P \left[\frac{\partial^2 u_n}{\partial \{d_g\}^2} \right] + (M_1 + M_2) \left[\frac{\partial^2 \theta_n}{\partial \{d_g\}^2} \right] \tag{100}$$

Based on the results obtained for the second derivatives of natural displacements with respect to global displacements, given in Equations (90) and (95), and using a local shear force Q to replace the bending moments ($Q = (M_1 + M_2)/L$), we arrive at the expression of the geometric stiffness matrix referred to the global coordinate system.

$$[K_g] = \frac{P}{L} \begin{bmatrix} s^2 & -cs & 0 & -s^2 & cs & 0 \\ -cs & c^2 & 0 & cs & -c^2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -s^2 & cs & 0 & s^2 & -cs & 0 \\ cs & -c^2 & 0 & -cs & c^2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} + \frac{Q}{L} \begin{bmatrix} -2cs & c^2 - s^2 & 0 & 2cs & s^2 - c^2 & 0 \\ c^2 - s^2 & 2cs & 0 & s^2 - c^2 & -2cs & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 2cs & s^2 - c^2 & 0 & -2cs & c^2 - s^2 & 0 \\ s^2 - c^2 & -2cs & 0 & c^2 - s^2 & 2cs & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \tag{101}$$

In the local system (i.e. assuming $\beta = 0$), the geometric matrix is shown below. Note that it is the same matrix obtained in Eq. (64).

$$[K_g] = \frac{1}{L} \begin{bmatrix} 0 & Q & 0 & 0 & -Q & 0 \\ Q & P & 0 & -Q & -P & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -Q & 0 & 0 & Q & 0 \\ -Q & -P & 0 & Q & P & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \tag{102}$$

Appendix A – The Principle of Contragradiency

The transformation matrix $[T]$ whose transpose relates the variation of displacements in global and natural systems, in Eq. (28), is the same matrix that relates forces in global and natural systems, in Eq. (39). This corresponds to the Principle of Contragradiency of structural analysis.

Therefore, the relation of Eq. (39) could also be derived from the Principle of Virtual Displacements, considering that the work performed by forces going through virtual displacements in the global and natural systems is equal. This is seen in Eq. (A1), where the virtual work must hold for an arbitrary virtual displacement. Writing the natural displacements in terms of global displacements, in Eq. (A2), and canceling it from the both sides of Eq. (A2), we obtain in Eq. (A3) the same relation of Eq. (39).

$$\{\delta d_g\}^T \{f_g\} = \{\delta d_n\}^T \{f_n\} \quad (\text{A1})$$

$$\{\delta d_g\}^T \{f_g\} = \left([T]^T \{\delta d_g\}\right)^T \{f_n\} \quad (\text{A2})$$

$$\{f_g\} = [T] \{f_n\} \quad (\text{A3})$$

References

- [1] Rangel, R.L. *Educational Tool for Structural Analysis of Plane Frame Models with Geometric Nonlinearity*. MSc thesis, Pontifical Catholic University of Rio de Janeiro (PUC-Rio), Brazil, 2019.
- [2] Crisfield, M.A. *Non-Linear Finite Element Analysis of Solids and Structures (vol. 1)*. John Wiley & Sons, 1991.
- [3] Souza, R.M. *Force-Based Finite Element for Large Displacement Inelastic Analysis of Frames*. PhD thesis, University of California, Berkeley, USA, 2000.
- [4] Baião, M.V. *Análise Não Linear de Estruturas com Rigidez Axial*. BSc thesis, Fluminense Federal University (UFF), Brazil, 2017.
- [5] Yaw, L.L. *2D Corotational Beam Formulation*. Walla Walla University, 2009.
- [6] Cavalcanti, D.B., Rangel, R.L., Martha, L.F. Nonlinear analysis of inelastic frames considering a corotational approach and plasticity by layers: a discussion about computational implementation. *XLIII Ibero-Latin American Congress on Computational Methods in Engineering (CILAMCE 2022)*, Foz do Iguacu, Brazil, November, 2022.
- [7] Rangel, R.L. *Corotational Stiffness Matrices for 3D Truss Elements*. Centre Internacional de Mètodes Numèrics a l'Enginyeria (CIMNE), Spain, 2023.
- [8] Rangel, R.L. *Corotational Stiffness Matrices for 2D Frame Elements*. Centre Internacional de Mètodes Numèrics a l'Enginyeria (CIMNE), Spain, 2023.
- [9] Rangel, R.L., Martha, L.F. Educational tool for the analysis of structures with geometric nonlinearity. *XXXIX Ibero-Latin American Congress on Computational Methods in Engineering (CILAMCE 2018)*, Paris/Compiègne, France, November 11-14, 2018.
- [10] Rangel, R.L., Martha, L.F. Implementation of a user-controlled structural analysis module with geometric nonlinearity. *25th International Congress of Mechanical Engineering (COBEM 2019)*, Uberlândia, Brazil, October 20-25, 2019.
- [11] Rangel, R.L., Martha, L.F. Programa para análise geometricamente não linear de pórticos por meio de um controle extensivo do usuário. *XL Ibero-Latin American Congress on Computational Methods in Engineering (CILAMCE 2019)*, Natal, Brazil, November 11-14, 2019.
- [12] Rangel, R.L., Martha, L.F. Ftool 5.0: Nonlinear, stability and natural vibration analyses. *XLI Ibero-Latin American Congress on Computational Methods in Engineering (CILAMCE 2020)*, November 16-19, 2020.
- [13] Martha, L.F., Rangel, R.L. FTOOL: Three decades of success as an educational program for structural analysis. *XLIII Ibero-Latin American Congress on Computational Methods in Engineering (CILAMCE 2022)*, Foz do Iguacu, Brazil, November 21-25, 2022.
- [14] Dias, C.L., Rangel, R.L., Martha, L.F. Nonlinear analysis in Ftool with semi-rigid connections: a partial development. *XLI Ibero-Latin American Congress on Computational Methods in Engineering (CILAMCE 2020)*, November 16-19, 2020.
- [15] Resende, C.H.B., Rangel, R.L., Lopes, P.C., Martha, L.F. An OOP architecture for the implementation of dynamic and nonlinear effects in structural analysis. *14th World Congress on Computational Mechanics (WCCM XIV) and European Congress on Computational Methods in Applied Sciences and Engineering (ECCOMAS 2020)*, January 11-15, 2021.
- [16] Cavalcanti, D.B., Rangel, R.L., Martha, L.F. Numerical experiments to assess the performance of different formulations and solution algorithms for geometrically nonlinear analysis of two-dimensional frames. *XLIII Ibero-Latin American Congress on Computational Methods in Engineering (CILAMCE 2022)*, Foz do Iguacu, Brazil, November 21-25, 2022.
- [17] Cavalcanti, D.B., Rangel, R.L., Martha, L.F. Structural analysis with nonlinear behavior: The importance of going beyond the line. *XLIII Ibero-Latin American Congress on Computational Methods in Engineering (CILAMCE 2022)*, Foz do Iguacu, Brazil, November 21-25, 2022.
- [18] Burgos, R.B., Martha, L.F., Rodrigues, M.A.C., Rangel, R.L. Modelling of the P- δ effect using interpolating functions. *XLII Ibero-Latin American Congress on Computational Methods in Engineering and III Pan-American Congress on Computational Mechanics (CILAMCE-PANACM 2021)*, November 9-12, 2021.
- [19] Rodrigues, M.A.C., Burgos, R.B., Rangel, R.L., Martha, L.F. An integrated formulation to predict pre and post-critical behavior of frames. *XLII Ibero-Latin American Congress on Computational Methods in Engineering and III Pan-American Congress on Computational Mechanics (CILAMCE-PANACM 2021)*, November 9-12, 2021.
- [20] Rodrigues, M.A.C., Guimarães, P.H.A., Burgos, R.B., Rangel, R.L., Martha, L.F. Influence evaluation of high-order terms in the strain tensor for a complete geometric nonlinear analysis with Timoshenko element. *XLIII Ibero-Latin American Congress on Computational Methods in Engineering (CILAMCE 2022)*, Foz do Iguacu, Brazil, November 21-25, 2022.